

LEXICAL-SEMANTIC CHANGES IN BORROWINGS

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Abstract. *This article covers the issues of lexical semantic changes in borrowings and nationalization of foreign words.*

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It is known that in the period after the introduction of the law on the state language, the desire to revise the adopted words and terms in the Uzbek language, especially international terms, to study and analyze their proportionality with the language norms has increased. Of course, thanks to such efforts, a lot of work has been done in the field of preserving the purity of our language and using its internal capabilities. However, as there is the norm in every work, if the work is not carried out based on a certain norm and scientific basis in terms of changing the words and terms in our consumption or accepting new ones instead of them, we can see confusion arise, necessary words and terms fall out of use due to artificial violence, inappropriate words and terms enter our language. It is necessary to avoid a foreign word that can be inappropriately borrowed into the language, but it is not acceptable to oppose any appropriation, its replacement. Language develops mainly on the basis of internal possibilities, and also on the basis of external (linguistic) influences. In fact, due to mutual economic and cultural ties, borrowing foreign words is a characteristic of all languages in the world. The Uzbek language is also active in this process.

When the Uzbek language received the status of the state language, the nationalization of our vocabulary became stronger. In the last three or four years, terms have been updated so much that it is not easy to define their scope. Because intellectuals, experts, students and teachers, wishing to raise our native language to a position worthy of it, found hundreds of nice and favorable terms related to their fields, and our language began to get rich very quickly from this noble action.

Dozens of words such as “iqtibos – citation”, “tashhis – diagnosis”, “mushhih – corrector” can be examples of this. But as with every good thing there is a bad side, in some cases when one comes a term that came from Western languages through Russian language or Russian science and technology, one is forced to uzbekize it in any way possible. Often this ends with a very funny result. For example, furthering the meaning of the plain word “подтяжка” to “a device that can be pulled and tied with shoulder straps to hold pants”, isn't it a mockery of our language? “Подтяжка” has alternatives, such as “osma kamar” or, if we look at history a little, “hamoyil”.

However, if we can't find a suitable substitute for a specific word term from the treasury of our human language, then it seems better to leave the popularized terms that have been used so far, instead of inventing funny inventions. Each language has its own national nature, its own internal laws. Ignoring it, or not paying attention to it, meddling in language phenomena, arbitrarily trying to introduce something “new” into the language will not lead to the expected result, it will confuse people and will waste a lot of money.

Which terms should we keep and which should we update? For example, if we use the term “tibbiyot (medicine)” instead of “медицина”, if we use “muhandis (engineer)” instead of

“инженер”, if we use “matbaa (printing)” instead of “полиграфия”, “mutanosib (proportional)” instead of “пропорционал” etc. we will manage only one direction of our speech.

If we compare the speech, or rather the style of the text, to a specific tune, then the use of Russian and European words mixed in the text seems to add western instruments to the oriental sounds, which is clearly not acceptable to everyone. But, it is clear that we can't do it now even after the Russian and European language revolutions.

In particular, it is impossible to do business without such terms in dozens of fields of science, technology and national economy that were not developed or newly appeared in our country. Calling “broadcast” as “havo mavjlari (airwaves)”, “safe” as “po‘lat sandiq (steel chest)”, “television” as “oynai jahon (mirror of the world)” is not nationalization of terms, but nothing more than the destruction of them. After all, if we begin to uzbekize the terms such as “hertz”, “ampere”, “volt”, “station”, “tractor”, “diesel”, “photon”, “accumulator” from the beginning, won't it become more difficult to understand and convey the knowledge of the relevant fields instead of making it easier? Or, let's take “мебель”. What a beautiful, concise word. Despite the fact that it is completely integrated into our language and is easy to pronounce, they demand that it should be removed and replaced by the two words “uy jihozi (home furnishing)”.

After all, home furnishing is a broad concept, it includes, for example, a curtain or a carpet, but these are not furniture. From the observations on the uzbekization of terms, we came to the conclusion that there are thousands of international terms that did not exist in the Russian language and for this reason they were adopted from foreign languages into the Russian language, from which they also entered the Uzbek language (such as “техника, электр, оптика, мотор, фотография (technology, electricity, optics, motor, photography)” – if there is no alternative to them in the vocabulary of our language – it is correct to give their transliteration rather than translation.

Dozens of words that existed in our language before and whose meaning has been somewhat updated with the requirements of today's conditions, such as “mumtoz (classic)”, “bo‘nak (prepayment)”, “tasnif (classification)”, “devonxona (office)”, and in general these research in the direction should be approved. Our language is a powerful, rich language. We want it to develop further, according to Oybek, to be rich and wealthy, not to be impoverished at all. The only way to do this is to preserve the existing scientific and technical innovations that have been accepted and assimilated for a long time, not to destroy them in vain, but to nationalize only the part of our language that does not fit the current position and status of our language.

During the transition to a market economy in our country, more and more terms are entering our language. A certain part of them is uzbekized based on the capabilities of our mother tongue and a certain part is used as an international adaptation.

The following cases can be observed in the use of economic terms in the Uzbek language and the chairman of the Terminology Committee, Odil Yaqubov, says: “Many terms have been uzbekized based on the capabilities of our language. In this case, a group of terms is given with ready-made alternatives in Uzbek, a certain part is translated and used and a part is created based on the rules of the Uzbek language. For example, аукцион-kimoshdi (auction), маклер-dallol (broker), коммерсант-tijoratchi (merchant), комиссионные вознаграждения-vositachilik haqi (brokerage fee), экономика-iqtisodiyot (economy), чек на предъявителя-oq chek (impersonal check), акционер-aksiyador (shareholder), бизнесмен-bizneschi (businessman) and others”.

Another direction is the borrowing of international terms used in most countries of the world into the Uzbek language. It should be noted here that it is difficult to find an Uzbek alternative to all the new terms. Therefore, most of them are used in the languages of most countries of the world in one form – in their original form, and such use is useful for the exchange of information among businessmen of the world. For example, an auditor, an accountant, a currency, a lease, a manager.

Certain terms are used differently in different alternatives. For example, the term “акционерное общество” in Russian is used in Uzbek versions such as “aksionerlik jamiyati, hissadorlik jamiyati, aksiyadorlik jamiyati, aksiyadorlar jamiyati, aksioner jamiyat (joint-stock company), the term “бартер (barter)” is given with the versions “mol ayirboshlash, tovar ayirboshlash, muvoza, barter” and the term “демпинг” in variants is “demping, arzonga sotish, narxni tashlash, molni chetga juda past narxda sotish”. Of course, such differences confuse experts in the field and make it difficult to exchange information. Therefore, achieving the main principle in terminology – “one term for one concept” remains the most urgent issue.

In recent years, interest in the meaning of borrowed words, their impact on the semantics of words in the Uzbek language lexicon and their adaptation to the language in terms of meaning has increased in recent years. “This problem, which is closely related to issues such as the semantic structure of the word, the lexicographic interpretation of the word, monosemy, polysemy, is of fundamental importance not only for semasiology, but also for other linguistic debates that study the vocabulary of the language (lexicology, lexicography, onomasiology, etymology, etc.) is emphasized again and again.

Much work has been done on the causes and general trends of semantic changes in adopted words in Western languages. These works are valuable sources in studying the reasons for the transfer of lexical acquisitions from one language to another and their meaning changes in interpreting. It is known that word borrowing occurs initially in the case of a word and some of its lexical meanings, and its semantic structure is not fully acquired. Because the context in which the meaning of borrowing is fully given and expressed is not yet formed in the initial period when it enters the language.

After all, it is accepted only through the expressive lexical meaning of things and objects that are accepted in a subordinate relationship depending on the mutual cultural relationship of peoples. A foreign word gradually begins to be used in connection with certain lexical units in the language. It takes certain forms of use in speech. Linguists try to find a semantically equivalent words from their mother tongue. Therefore, if there is such a unity of language, the meaning of appropriation will be clarified and concreted again. Its place of use in the language is defined and its use is actualized.

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